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Report on federated data access scenarios

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1. Executive Summary

The goal of the “Genomic Data Infrastructure” project is to generate a framework and all the tools to share human genomic data and associated phenotypical and clinical data. European and national regulations require that these types of data are protected.

Sharing of sensitive data needs to comply with law that implies the use of secure storage and authorised access. In a federated scenario there could be several ways data could be accessed by interested researchers. We need to distinguish, for example, between cases in which the data is accessed and analysed remotely in the storing facility versus the cases in which the data is downloaded to the requester’s premises. Other factors to be considered include type of data, type of permissions (full access to the data or partial, meaning access only to a section of the genomic sequences), types of analysis and types of federated approach in which we are situated (relation among the nodes forming the network). The scope of this deliverable is to analyse, describe and compare the different possibilities to access data in a federated context like the one GDI is building. In this document we provide an analysis of key factors to consider, including:

1. Remote and virtualized querying of data
2. Remote and virtualized access and visualisation of data
3. Running pipelines or workflows at the node hosting the data
4. Running interactive environments
5. Downloading of data to the requester premises or to the cloud
6. Access to aggregated results from federated analyses

Existing tools for data access include graphical user interfaces (GUI), command line interfaces, interactive environment, download and copy of data. All these could be used for access individual-level or aggregated data, and that would have different legal and technical implications. The comprehensive landscape description, including all considerations of these factors will inform and instruct GDI Pillar II technological design and development. Thus, the consideration listed here will serve as bases for the subsequent work within GDI.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Scope of the deliverable

The aim of the “Genomic Data Infrastructure” project is to enable human genomic and associated phenotypical and clinical data sharing in Europe. For such data sharing, data submitters have to deposit data in appointed repositories, where other researchers are able to find data of interest and receive access authorisation.

The scope of this deliverable is to analyse, describe and compare the different possibilities to access deposited data. Within this document we describe the different needs for data access, according to the different use cases in the GDI project. This has been done taking into consideration the specific requirements for data access by each use case, analysed in WP7. Subsequently, we describe the technology underlying the various scenarios, and the work that has been done to develop them. This is a descriptive report, intended to be useful for the part of the project working on the technological solutions.

4. Introduction

Data related to and obtained from human beings is considered personal data, and protected by the European General Data Protection regulation (GDPR), in addition to national and/or other local regulations. Data related to genomics and health is considered “special category” data by GDPR, and its processing is very strongly regulated.

The goal of the “Genomic Data Infrastructure” project is to generate a framework (Pillar I) and the necessary tools (Pillar II) to share human genomic data and associated phenotypical and clinical data. Lawful and responsible sharing can only be achieved using technical solutions for secure storage and authorised access. The solutions should minimise the risk and impact of errors and prevent misuse of data.

To accomplish this, the selected working model is the assembly of independent local repositories into a federation, where every federated node keeps its autonomy while sharing a common set of interfaces, standard operating procedures (SOPs) and governance¹.

There are at least two reasons why it can be good to provide data processing “close to” the data holder: safety and practicality of data transfer.

Regarding safety, methods enabling accessing and analysing the data inside the jurisdiction of the data controller are safer than those that require making a copy of the data elsewhere, particularly abroad. When data is accessed directly in the hosting facility, thus offered for analysis without replicating it to the users' facility, data holders can decide to delegate providing compute services to a trusted third party, typically an entity specialised in providing advanced IT services.

¹ Thorogood et al, 2021: [10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100032](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100032)

Regarding practicality of data transfer, genomic data can be very large and many research questions do not require access to the whole genome of the cohorts and rather focus on individual genes /clusters of genes, perhaps even from a subset of the samples in the cohorts. For that reason, downloading the whole dataset into the requester premises when it is unnecessary to access all the data would not comply with the data minimisation principle and would be a waste of precious resources

Considering the above-mentioned reasons, keeping the analysis process close to where the data is hosted might be a more suitable solution, but increases the computing infrastructure requirements at the source. The processing workload of genomic data is also quite intensive, requiring powerful computers with significant amounts of working memory and enough storage for holding the intermediate and end-result data. This might pose a challenge for researchers interested in secondary use to have enough capacity on their own facilities to transfer, store and analyse such data. However, the size of the data and analysis workload can vary greatly according to the process to be deployed; file browsing or visualisation with a tool can be light-weight, while discovering genome structural variants or imputing non-sequenced regions or de novo assembly, are very resource demanding. Thus, these are factors that have to be taken into account..

4.1 Assumptions and definitions used in the current document

The current report is prepared in parallel to other 1+MG and GDI efforts without final conclusions. Therefore, the report is written with definitions that might be particular only to this report and assumptions that might be clarified further in the future..

Definition 1: We refer to “user” as the individual with an interest in accessing data.

Assumption 1: The user has already discovered the data through any available mechanism (GDI User Portal, GDI Beacon or directly from an accession id cited in a paper) and has been granted access to either:

1. The entire file or database
2. A fragment or a set of fragments of a file or section of the database
3. Only to aggregated data, precalculated by the data controller or by any algorithm supplied by the user

Definition 2: “Data” refers to genomic data or associated pheno-clinical data.

Assumption 2: Although “federated data access” could apply to many different types of data (e.g. images), no other use cases are considered here apart from those that would likely be part of GDI objectives. Namely:

1. Genomic files:
 - a. Raw sequencing files for exomes or whole genomes (i.e. Fastq)
 - b. Alignment files (i.e. BAM and CRAM)
 - c. Variant calling files (i.e. VCF)

2. Pheno-clinical files:
 - a. Raw text files (e.g. comma separated value files - CSV)
 - b. Processed, enriched files (e.g. Phenopackets)
3. Pheno-clinical Data residing in
 - a. Relational Databases (e.g. PostgreSQL)
 - b. NoSQL databases (e.g. MongoDB or ElasticSearch)

4.2 Applying permission granularity to GDI data sources

The table below shows a simplified view of the general difficulty of applying the granularity of permissions to the mentioned sources of data.

	Whole	Partial	Aggregations
FASTQ	Easy	n/p	n/p
BAM/CRAM	Easy	Moderate	Moderate
VCF	Easy	Moderate	Moderate
CSV	Easy	Moderate	Moderate
SQL DB	Easy	Complex	Hard
NoSQL DB	Easy	Complex	Hard

Difficulty: Easy < Moderate < Hard < Complex < Not possible (n/p)

4.2.1 An example: applying permission granularity to a SQL Database

As an example, applying permissions to a SQL DB could be easy, complex or hard.

It is easy when the goal is to provide or deny access to a whole database, given that authorising for some (whole) databases in the server is part of the user creation process.

Granting partial access to data could be done by giving access to a limited set of tables (ideally to *views*, instead of *tables*), to some rows (*horizontal partition*) or to some columns (*vertical partition*) or to some columns inside some rows. In a relational database, the natural way of restricting access to columns or rows is by creating a *view* that enforces the desired filters, e.g. if a table contains data for the whole cohort, the view could restrict access to just men or to just women, to patients with glaucoma or to patients from the oncology department. As the view definition includes the list of columns to show, the columns could be selected at that point.

Views are a pragmatic option if the same restriction (e.g. "patients related to the oncology department") is requested by many data users, however they become non sustainable if every user requires a different set of restriction combinations, e.g. of disease, gender, age range and ethnicity.

Views can also contain aggregated data instead of source rows and columns. The same restrictions mentioned for partial data apply here. However, if the aggregated data results are dynamic (result of an *ad hoc* query) or based on a previous restriction (partial data access), an additional layer of complexity is added. As database permissions are applied to database objects (e.g, tables, views, stored procedures), a potential solution would be to create a table, view or stored procedure dynamically (*ad hoc*), grant permissions to the user to that object, and destroy the object back after an expiration time or when the user session is closed. Although this is possible, there are potential side effects that make this hard in practice, like limitations on the maximum number of objects that a database admits, or impact in the backup procedures, etc.

5. Federated data access scenarios landscape description

This document discusses the scenarios of accessing data that is distributed among the participant nodes of a Federation. Accessing distributed data adds further layers of complexity to local or remote data access. The next section describes an idealised process, some considerations for the federation approach, and several considerations for different use cases of data access.

5.1 Data analysis steps

The purpose of a user requesting access to the data is usually to perform some analysis, that could be simple, like browsing the data, or complex, like training an artificial intelligence model.

Typically, and in a simplified view, the process of analysing data to obtain any kind of result could require different steps (see figure 1):

1. Browse or explore manually the source data
2. Profile the data to get a statistical description of it. Save it for further reference
3. Segment the data to leave only the relevant records and variables
4. Pre-process the data in preparation for the analysis. This step includes, e.g.. planning harmonisation, conversion of units, bucketing, quality control and pruning...
5. Process the source data through different steps, obtaining intermediate results
6. Review the results, applying quality control protocols, etc.
7. Analyse data to obtain final results
8. Inspect or perform quality controls of the analysis. This might lead to Iterate the process to further analyse the data, to correct discovered errors or remove artefacts
9. Save the results

5.1.1 Additional complexity in the federation scenarios

When working with local data, generated and owned by the analyst, these steps already present significant challenges. These challenges are bigger in a federated data access scenario, e.g.:

1. Data to analyse could be distributed across several locations (nodes)
2. Data processing infrastructure could be at a different location to where the data is stored
3. Preferred or known tools may not be available at the processing infrastructure
4. Cloud and HPC computing services could offer different resources (type of CPU; amount of memory, maximum time allowed for a process to run, etc.)
5. Limitations to access all the necessary data could make it impossible to perform certain steps or analyses

In the Figure 2 example, looking for genetic variants that could cause a mono-genic disease on an individual (case), the same procedure could be applied to cases found in different countries. The required tools: FastQC, the read aligner, the BAM post-processor (e.g. GATK²), a genomic browser (like IGV³ or like bam.io.bio⁴), etc. should ideally be available at each of the computing infrastructures

² <https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/>

³ <https://igv.org/>

⁴ <https://bam.io.bio/>

or it should be allowed to deploy them (or alternatives proven to deliver comparable results). Also some processes could require, e.g. 64GB of RAM, and such computer configuration should be available at the node where the data is hosted.

The case of federated analysis could be indeed more challenging if the analysis starts from pre-processed files, like the alignments, additional checks are needed and other challenges appear (like the parameters of the alignment, version of the genome, etc). Even when starting from FASTQs, some parameters that could differ among nodes may be considered (e.g. the insert size).

5.2 Data access scenarios

The data analysis steps mentioned above are typically performed using at least one of the categories of tools listed below:

1. Remote and virtualized access and visualisation of data through a graphical user interface (GUI), e.g. phenotypes, clinical data, genomic variants
2. Remote and virtualized querying of data through command line interface (CLI), like *bash*, e.g. to look for specific lines in a file or to browse its structure
3. Running pipelines or workflows at the node serving the data (e.g. computing; running analysis pipelines), which implies running tools as commands or embedded in containers (like Docker or Singularity)
4. Running interactive environments like RStudio, that allows for iterative or *ad hoc* analysis of the data.
5. When allowed, download of data to copy the data to another location (e.g. local HPC cluster; cloud provider)
6. Egress aggregated results from federated analyses

GDI data access scenarios, then, result from the combination of the elements described so far:

1. Data source types: file types, databases...
2. Permission granularity: whole, partial, aggregated
3. Categories of steps in an analysis: browsing, filtering, processing, quality controls
4. Diversity arising from a federated approach: distribution, availability of tools, etc.

As the number of potential combinations is huge, this document doesn't describe all of them, but rather focuses on aspects to take into account when designing the GDI infrastructure and governance.

5.2.1 Considerations for Remote and Virtualized Access to files

“Remote” and “Virtualized” access

In the context of this document, we are making a distinction between “Remote” and “Virtualized” access.

- Remote access means using the user's computer to access data located elsewhere. This operation implies establishing a connection from the local tool (e.g, RStudio) to a remote source of data (e.g, a SQL database located outside of your network).
- Virtualized access means accessing the data located elsewhere from a (virtual) computer that usually is located close to the data. Typically this virtual computer is hosted in a general cloud or in a trusted cloud environment.

The term “local file” refers to files that are stored in storage devices that are physically connected to a physical computer or to a virtual disk in a virtual computer. Remote files are files hosted in a storage device that is physically connected to *another* computer but that are accessible from the local computer through a given technical solution, typically by “mounting” the remote device as if it was a local device or, alternatively, by connecting to the remote device through a special protocol or interface. The former (*mounting*) makes the remote device look like a local device, hence is almost transparent to any tool wanting to access the files. The latter (*connecting*) requires some sort of intermediate step or interface, like a web page, to access the file. One example of access through a connection is accessing files hosted in Google Drive, which are accessed from a web page and edited by tools available to Google Drive or must be downloaded locally. It is possible, however, to install a tool in a local computer that integrates (*mounts*) Google Drive into the local file system, and hence making the access to them transparent to the local tools.

In both scenarios, to access the file a server is required that serves it to the local computer. The file server applies authorization rules and could indeed perform additional steps like decrypting files that are encrypted at rest.

	Whole	Partial	Aggregations
Remote access to files	Easy	Complex	Hard

Difficulty: Easy < Moderate < Hard < Complex < Not possible (n/p)

5.2.2 Considerations for Remote and Virtualized Access to databases

Databases could be local (like SQLite⁵) or managed by a server (like PostgreSQL⁶). Local databases usually are single files which are internally organised as a database. Server managed databases have two software components: a database server and a database client. The client computer runs the client software which handles the connection, requests and responses to and from the database server. We are not considering local databases as this is essentially like accessing a file.

Both remote and virtualized access to a database server require a direct connection from the client tool to the database server, the only available mechanism for limiting the access of a given user is through the features that the database server provides and that should be administered by a person or automated in a secure way.

Some database products provide very granular authorization, allowing for granting access to a set of records (rows in the case of a relational database) or fields (columns in a relational database). However, other databases only allow granting access to the whole database or to whole tables or documents, but not to just some parts of them.

	Whole	Partial	Aggregations
Remote access to a DB	Easy	Complex	Complex

Difficulty: Easy < Moderate < Hard < Complex < Not possible (n/p)

5.2.3 Considerations for running pipelines

Pipelines and workflows are constructs that encapsulate a process, that is: several steps that run one after the other, often using the output of the previous step as input of the next one.

A pipeline may include scripts and tools, developed by the same person writing the pipeline or by other people. . When the developer of the pipeline has not also developed the included scripts and tools, he or she might face bigger constraints to adapt them to the required level of granularity.

For sensitive data (like the one managed by GDI) the recommendation is that files are always encrypted *at rest*⁷, this is, while on disk vs while on memory.. Most of the popular tools are not capable of working using encrypted data or to generate encrypted results. This adds a new constraint to the process.

One solution to mitigate having to deal with encryption along the pipeline is to stream or pipe the results of one step into the next one, hence the data is never "at rest" and could flow unencrypted

⁵ <https://www.sqlite.org/index.html>

⁶ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_at_rest

between steps. The design of a solution like that is that only the first step needs to deal with encryption and the results are handled directly to the second step, hence never being saved as a file until the last step is done. Therefore the first step is a decryption tool or command, and the very last step is an encryption tool or command.

Unfortunately many tools are not capable of accepting one stream as input and generating a stream as output, and they assume that the data is stored as a file and they require a file path as input and a file path for the output..

A pipeline could be processed in a local environment that is controlled by the user or in an environment where the user is constrained to available resources (specially software and procedures available, Cloud environments, administered virtual machines, or HPC clusters are kinds of these managed environments. Managed environments introduce additional considerations on the type of computer resources available to the user.

A pipeline is a chain of tools, hence, the considerations mentioned in the previous sections apply to each of them individually, but, when chained, there is an additional requirement: all tools must be able to handle the same level of permission granularity or the pipeline would not be able to perform its duty. E.g, If Step 1 is able to use parts of a file (partial permission), but Step 2 is not, then the grosser granularity is the one that actually drives the whole pipeline.

5.2.4 Considerations for running interactive environments

Interactive environments like RStudio⁸ or Jupyter⁹ notebooks have similar considerations as running pipelines or remotely accessing files/databases at the data hosting node. They are capable of working with as much or as little data is provided to them. However, given that their purpose is to allow for freedom in exploration, if the provided data is minimal the exploration space will also be minimal, which could make the tools actually useless.

	Whole	Partial	Aggregations
Accessing files or DBs through Interactive environments	Easy	Complex	n/p

Difficulty: Easy < Moderate < Hard < Complex < Not possible (n/p)

5.2.5 Considerations for data downloading

Downloading is the traditional way users get access to data from others to be analysed. However, when data is big, this poses both technical and legal/ethical challenges. Technical, since the network needs to be fast enough and the receiving party must have enough storage available. Legal and ethical, because allowing a user to download data requires absolute trust in how the receiving

⁸ <https://posit.co/products/open-source/rstudio/>

⁹ <https://jupyter.org/>

party will treat the data. Additionally, the GDPR requirement for data minimisation¹⁰ must be taken into account.

	Whole	Partial	Aggregations
Downloading files	Easy	Complex	n/p

Difficulty: Easy < Moderate < Hard < Complex < Not possible (n/p)

5.2.6 Considerations for aggregated results

Aggregated results could be pre-computed by the data controller or generated on demand according to the user needs (by a constrained set of options or by an algorithm provided by the user). Returning just aggregated results seems a sound solution to avoid data disclosure. However it introduces additional challenges to the user:

1. Most of the control and analysis steps could be not possible because they require access to the original data.
 - a. One mitigation strategy is providing pre-calculated profiles and additional statistical descriptions of the data. This could help to understand the data to be analysed. One example could be the quality control reports provided by the EGA^{11,12,13}.
 - b. However, if the aggregated results show some unexpected values, e.g. an unforeseen broad standard deviation, it could be very hard to track down where these values come from, as it could require browsing the results or performing additional descriptive analysis on them.
2. As the actual data used for calculating the results is opaque to the user. In the case that reproducibility is required, e.g. by a journal referee, it could be very hard to guarantee that the originally used data is there in its original shape. As this issue affects other scenarios, we have discussed it in a dedicated section (section *Traceability or reproducibility of the results for partial or aggregated data*)

5.2.7 Traceability or reproducibility of the results for partial or aggregated data

As described above, granting access to parts of the dataset or returning just aggregated results are two approaches that try to reduce the amount of shared data, especially when it is obvious that it would not be used in the planned analysis. These approaches, however, add challenges to both the traceability and reproducibility of the results.

¹⁰ <https://www.ru.nl/rdm/gdpr-research/gdpr-research-data-minimisation/>

¹¹ <https://filesportal.ega-archive.org/EGAF00005469847>

¹² <https://filesportal.ega-archive.org/EGAF00005469864>

¹³ <https://filesportal.ega-archive.org/EGAF00005469863>

Reproducibility is broadly based on having access to both the data and the algorithms used in a given analysis. These objects (data and algorithms) could both be assigned persistent IDs¹⁴ which would allow coming back to them at any point in time.

When data is preselected for a specific user, a new persistent ID (PID) must be generated for that specific subset of the data. Assuming that saving every tailored dataset would not be possible for the vast majority of data and infrastructure providers, a mechanism to regenerate the same exact tailored dataset must be provided. This information must be captured in the metadata associated with the newly generated PID.

The PID metadata, then, must include descriptions of (at least):

1. The PID of the original data
2. The IDs of the rows included in the tailored dataset
3. The IDs (names) of the variables included for each row
4. As most databases does not have a PID for every snapshot of it, a timestamp of the version of the record used in the analysis

Additionally the metadata for the tailored PID could include checksums for:

1. The whole tailored dataset
2. Each tailored record
3. Each column/variable

The dataset checksum would confirm if the dataset has been reconstructed correctly. In case the original and the reconstructed dataset checksums don't match, the comparison of the original record checksums with the reconstructed ones would allow to spot which records have not been properly reconstructed. In many cases, all records could end up not matching and that is usually due to one or more column/variable having an issue, comparing the original and reconstructed column checksums should help in detecting that issue.

A similar problem and a similar solution is described in the "Data Citation of Evolving Data: Recommendations of the Working Group on Data Citation (WGDC)"¹⁵ from RDA. This document exemplifies the complexity of providing a solution for this type of scenario.

5.2.8 Smart layers

Along this document there are many references to the constraints added to the process by the requirement of granting access to just part of the data. Most of them derive from the need to tailor the view that the user has on the data according to her/his permissions. There is a common principle for the most promising solutions (e.g. EGA QuickView¹⁶ or DataSHIELD¹⁷): setting up a layer between

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persistent_identifier

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/1406002#XG2FV0hKhaQ>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/ega-quickview>

¹⁷ <https://datashield.org/>

the user (or user' tools) and the data that is smart enough to gather the information about the permissions granted to the user and the delivery of the data.

This type of layer can check user identity, user permissions at any level of granularity, metadata for the data to access, build properly formatted tailored files (e.g. proper BAMs with headers and associated indexes), etc. A similar solution could be built, Indeed, for relational databases, where a preparation process can create *views*, *stored procedures* or *user functions* to which only a particular user would have access.

However, building a smart layer is an advanced challenge which could not be rebuilt at every computing service provider, and portable open source solutions should be built by the community.

Partial access to data increases 1) the challenge of sustainability, given the additional intelligence that must be included in the architecture, and 2) the scalability, as some of the mentioned solutions could handle a huge number of users (e.g. EGA QuickView or DataSHIELD), while others (i.e. per user database views) could eventually reach the limits of the tool being leveraged (e.g. number of users or number of database objects in a relational database server).

5.3 Tools that access data

5.3.1 Access through a graphical user interface (GUI)

In the context of GDI, graphical user interfaces could be used to browse the data or some charts generated from the data. For example, in the B1MG Proof of Concept (PoC) of Rare Diseases, local installations of the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP)¹⁸ were used to query and access data from different nodes through a graphical user interface. The PoC included visualising the alignments stored remotely at a local EGA instance through IGV¹⁹ making use of the GA4GH htsget standard^{20,21}, which loads the files to browse and keeps reading from them as the user zooms out, scrolls along a chromosome or jumps to another section of the genome (see Figure 3). In this scenario, according to the granularity of permissions, some solutions could be applied:

1. Access granted to the whole file
 - a. No action is required
2. Access granted to parts of the files
 - a. Generating the BAMs files (and indexes) a priori. The file must be generated and stored for the user.
 - b. Using a smart layer that allows access to the granted regions on the fly, obfuscating the ones not authorised.
3. Access to summary results is not applicable for this scenario

¹⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9324157/>

¹⁹ <https://software.broadinstitute.org/software/igv/>

²⁰ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/htsget.html>

²¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9932977/>

cBioPortal²² (Figure 4) exemplifies another use case: tools that require pre-processing of the data to be extracted, transformed and loaded (e.g. ETL pipeline). In the case of cBioPortal, CSV and MAF files must be loaded into the MySQL database that backs cBioPortal operations.

In this scenario, according to the granularity of permissions, some solutions could be applied:

4. Access granted to the whole file
 - a. No action is required
5. Access granted to parts of the files
 - a. Generating the CSV and MAF files (and indexes) a priori. The file must be generated and stored for the user and ingested into cBioPortal
 - b. Using a smart layer is not applicable in this case, except through a quite complex administration of the MySQL database server.
6. Access to summary results is not applicable for this scenario

²² <https://www.cbioportal.org/>

chromosome 6..

5.3.2 Querying through command line interface

Accessing data from a command line interface (CLI), like *bash* or GATK is similar to other operations that open a file and run over it. Some environments will include only a subset of “allowed” tools, to which the user needs to abide. For such cases, smart layers or preprocessing the files are available although not necessarily trivial, solutions.

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In many cases the tool is used to generate other files: an index, some summary stats, a sorted or recalibrated version of the file, etc.

Obviously for cases where only access to aggregated results is allowed, just browsing or subsampling makes sense, but not other types of operations.

5.3.3 Running interactive environments

Interactive environments like RStudio²³ or Jupyter²⁴ notebooks have similar requirements to GUI tools like IGV, meaning that they would be able to work with any data provided. If whole file or database access is allowed, there are no problems with this. If only partial access is provided, pre-processing the data would be the preferable solution. Although it depends on the specific study being performed, in most of the cases an aggregated results granularity would not be enough and challenging the purpose of accessing the data.

5.3.4 Download of data to copy the data to another location

Although, in principle, the goal of federation in GDI is to minimise data movement, some cases would require moving the data, e.g, moving the data from the data host to the designated computing environment.

Again, moving the whole file should be easy, while allowing access to parts of the file/s would require pre-processing. In this case, the pre-processing could be performed by a smart layer on the fly or by scheduled processes that leave customised files into the user inbox.

Although possible, downloading aggregated results files seems a trivial use case, as these files tend to be very small and the computing facility could indeed host a copy or a cache of them.

5.3.5 Running pipelines or workflows at the node

Once a user is granted access to a dataset, the analysis might entail performing analyses that require the execution of complex computer intensive processes in the same node where the data resides. The reasons could be that the data access permission does not allow to transfer data elsewhere or that the option to download the data is not ideal to the size of the dataset or not allowed due to regulatory restrictions. It is worth mentioning that the node could enforce restrictions on the processes being run.

One of the main considerations of this approach is that the node hosting the data needs to allocate computing resources to the user analysing the data. With this in mind, GDI might want to develop policies and/or envision financial and operational models and workflows to describe how these services could be provided. Upfront clarity on data use conditions upon discovery of a dataset might

²³ <https://posit.co/products/open-source/rstudio/>

²⁴ <https://jupyter.org/>

be key to save precious resources and time, since a user might decide not to request access to a dataset if it is not possible to download the data or run certain pipelines at the hosting node.

Nevertheless, it is desirable that analyses are organised in a reproducible workflow. This will allow comparison of results obtained on different datasets within one or several nodes and with previous results. However, developing pipelines is a time consuming task and the implementation might be different from one HPC or Cloud environment to another. Therefore, facilitating the implementation of pipelines at the nodes with a common standard might be key. In this sense, GA4GH has approved the Workflow Execution Service (WES) API, which describes a programmatic way to run and manage workflows and monitor over the web. This will allow the same containerised (e.g. with Docker or Singularity) workflow to run on various execution platforms running on various clouds/environments²⁵. The clients are able to launch workflows written in Common Workflow Language (CWL), Workflow Description Language (WDL) or Nextflow²⁶. This process is further facilitated if the workflow engine, such as Nextflow or an CWL implementation, supports the Task Execution Service (TES) API²⁷, which is able to connect the workflow to a compute backend to execute specific steps²⁸.

Finally, it is worth noting that there are websites such as BioContainers²⁹ that provide containers of many analytical tools, and resources such as nf-core³⁰ which provide a collection of curated Nextflow data analysis pipelines.

5.3.6 Access to aggregated results from federated analyses

In federated analyses, results from processes run across different nodes are aggregated centrally or at one of the nodes. In the rare disease field, zero-sided matchmaking³¹ aims to identify candidate disease causing genes with damaging genetic variants on patients with common phenotypes. The application of zero-sided matchmaking across the nodes in the network as a federated analysis approach would increase the sample size and the chances of finding statistically significant associations.

A form of federated analysis is federated learning, in which it is possible to train algorithms on federated datasets without the need to move them to a centralised platform. The key steps of such an approach are to define the machine learning model, to select the datasets that will be used for the training and to configure the parameters. In order to orchestrate the analysis across the nodes, a separate service, or one of the nodes, needs to operate as a central node that will orchestrate the analysis across the network. Federated learning requires the implementation of specific tools such as

²⁵ <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

²⁶ https://starterkit.ga4gh.org/docs/starter-kit-apis/wes/wes_overview/

²⁷ <https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas>

²⁸

https://www.ga4gh.org/news_item/ga4gh-tes-api-bringing-compatibility-to-task-execution-across-hpc-systems-the-cloud-and-beyond/

²⁹ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

³⁰ <https://nf-co.re/>

³¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9133175/>

a federated learning framework (e.g. Flower³²) and managers of the machine learning lifecycle (e.g. MLFlow³³).

Projects such as CINECA³⁴ and Genomed4All³⁵ are evaluating these approaches on genomic data, and their findings might be highly informative to GDI.

One of the advantages of federated analyses and federated learning is that in principle they could be applied even if the user does not have permission to visualise or download the datasets at the node. It is only necessary to have permission to run analyses on the node and be allowed to collect the results. However, it might be challenging to evaluate that the results of the analysis are summarised or aggregated to a level that don't include any identifiable or sensitive data or that they cannot be coerced into revealing identifiable aspects of the original training data. For this reason, it might be necessary to pre-define which such approaches are implemented and enabled across the participating nodes.

6. Conclusions, Impact and next steps

From the landscape description provided in this document, we can appreciate the complexity of the factors that are implicated in defining a modality to access data in a federated context. Indeed, many elements need to be taken in consideration and they have various interdependencies. Thus, the type of data to be accessed and the analysis to be performed influence the type of permissions to be requested and granted. Similarly, the type of federated setting influences the way the data is accessed. Although intricate, it is instrumental to understand this puzzle and take into account the right pieces that compose all the possible data access scenarios envisioned in the GDI federated network. Given this report will be useful for framework and technology design, a failure in being comprehensive in this step (having some aspects unexplored), would leave certain needs uncovered by the technological solutions and the framework generated in other WPs of the project.

This report will be handed to pillar I and pillar II partners, and the content information will enter the pipeline of the GDI project. Nonetheless, the communication and dialogue over these aspects will not be restricted to this unique report, but will continue during the project timeline, through direct exchanges, and thanks to the authors' involvement in the technology development itself carried out in Pillar II.

7. References

References are inserted as footnotes throughout the text.

³² <https://flower.dev/>

³³ <https://mlflow.org/>

³⁴ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/federated-data-analysis>

³⁵ <https://genomed4all.eu/>

